

antly related to the level of stem infestation by *M. separatella*. Although stem infestation was similar among treatments, the percentage of empty grains was significantly higher at higher N levels.

Yield was relatively low because of low soil fertility. Analysis of number of productive tillers per unit area indicates that the high density crop produced many panicles/m² but few grains/panicle. Yield did not increase with plant population, and seed costs and labor costs for transplanting were higher. High density planting was not economically viable. □

Effect of fertility and plant density on stem borer infestation and rice yield in Western Kenya.^a

	500,000 hills/ha			250,000 hills/ha		
	0 kg N/ha	60 kg N/ha	120 kg N/ha	0 kg N/ha	60 kg N/ha	120 kg N/ha
Hills with deadhearts ^b (%)	2.8 a	3.5 ab	8.5 b	5.3 ab	6.2 ab	15.4 c
Hills with whiteheads ^c (%)	1.9 a	4.0 ab	7.0 b	4.8 ab	9.2 bc	15.2 c
Stem infestation ^c (%)	70.0 a	72.0 a	74.0 a	73.0 a	81.0 a	83.0 a
Empty grains (%)	2.6 a	2.7 ab	4.9 c	2.4 a	2.8 b	4.1 c
Panicles/m ²	352 b	392 c	477 d	242 ab	201 a	330 b
Grains/panicle	108 a	107 a	111 a	313 b	315 b	359 b
Yield (t/ha)	1.9 a	1.9 ab	1.9 b	1.9 b	2.0 c	2.0 d

^aMeans in a row followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bDeadhearts and whiteheads were counted 60 and 120 days after transplanting, respectively. ^cRecorded at harvest.

Stem borers in various rice ecosystems in Kenya

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We surveyed incidence of stem borers, a serious rice pest in some Kenyan ecosystems. Rice is grown on small farms and in irrigated lowlands, rainfed uplands, and swamplands.

Lowland irrigated rice is the most important ecosystem, being a monoculture in areas of several thousand hectares. Upland rainfed rice is grown in small areas and rotated with maize or sorghum during the long rainy season. Swampy lowland rice is grown on marginal swampland in western Kenya where water can be 30 cm deep and tall varieties are planted.

Lepidopterous borers present are *Chilo partellus*, *Sesamia calamistis*, and *Maliarpha separatella*. The first two species are major pests of sorghum and maize and *M. separatella* is specific to rice. Dipterous borers are *Diopsis thoracica* and *D. apicalis*.

The survey included the western, central, and coastal provinces. At each location rice stalks at various growth stages were dissected. Infestation was recorded as percentages of hills and tillers

Stem borer incidence in various rice ecosystems in Kenya.

Rice ecosystem	Year	Hills infested (%)	Tillers infested (%)	Stem borers/hill (no.) ^a				Species composition (%)			
				C	D	M	S	C	D	M	S
Lowland irrigated (2 locations)	1981	95	41	0	0	4.5	.2	0	0	90	10
	1982	72	10	0	.3	.3	0	0	52	48	0
	Mean	83	25.5	0	.15	2.4	.1	0	26	69	5
Upland rainfed (6 locations)	1981	62	14	.1	.01	.1	0	50	6	44	0
	1982	16	8	.5	.05	.15	.1	12	32	44	12
	Mean	39	11.0	.3	.03	.12	.05	31	19	44	6
Swampy lowland (3 locations)	1982	53	5	0	.9	0	0	0	100	0	0
Flooded swamp (1 location)	1981	56	12	0	0	.8	0	0	0	100	0

^aC = *Chilo partellus*, D = *Diopsis* spp.; M = *Maliarpha separatella*, S = *Sesamia calamistis*.

infested. Species composition and average number of larvae, pupae, and pupal cases recovered per hill were recorded (see table).

Stem borer infestation generally was higher in lowland irrigated rice, with *M. separatella* predominating. *M. separatella* also infested flooded swamp rice, where other stem borers were absent. It damaged the crop at all growth stages and caused a large proportion of unfilled grains. *Diopsis* occurred more frequently in lowlands where water is available, but was not found in flooded swamps. It infested rice only at early vegetative phase

and caused characteristic deadhearts. Upland rainfed rice was infested more by sorghum and maize pests — *C. partellus* and *S. calamistis* — than lowland rice.

Different stem borer species and damage levels in various rice ecosystems require different control methods. Yield obtained from ecosystems other than lowland irrigated rice is low, making chemical control uneconomical. For upland rice, however, yield-improving practices such as crop rotation or intercropping with a leguminous crop tends to reduce stem borer population while increasing soil fertility. □

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